

DEEP LEARNING AS A TOOL OF QUANTUM ERROR REDUCTION IN QUANTUM IMAGE PROCESSING*

Krzysztof WERNER, Krzysztof CYRAN

Department of Computer Graphics, Vision, and Digital Systems,
Silesian University of Technology, Gliwice, Poland

Quantum image processing could be soon used to process very large images. Because of quantum superposition number of qubits required to encode images onto the quantum circuit is exponentially smaller than number of classical bits that would be used to accomplish the same. Quantum interference and entanglement allows than to perform some image processing on multiple computational paths. The size 1.5-hour long video of resolution of 108MPx (11664 x 9320 pixels), frame rate of 60 FPS and bitrate of 80 Mbps would equate to 3,88TB, while it could be encoded into the quantum computer using only 46 qubits. Using IBM Osprey as reference, which has 433 qubits, it could store $9 * 10^{116}$ hours of recording in this quality. The reality, however, prohibits researchers of using quantum computers for such large images. Quantum errors renders resulting images unusable.

In this paper we want to explore quantum error reduction, performed on classical computer. Especially we want to use deep learning to create the map of error correcting factors to be applied to resulting image. This notion of error correcting factors, that could be applied to any image, is supported by the experiments showing temporal stability of quantum errors in quantum sampling based computation described by Werner et al. [1]. We want to pair this error reduction method with Flexible Representation of Quantum Images (FRQI) by Le et al. in [2] or NEQR (Novel Enhanced Quantum Representation of images) by Zhang et al. [3]. Local Phase Image Quantum Encoding (LPIQE) method [4], in the effort to make quantum image processing a viable tool in Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era.

Materials & method

Phase Distortion Unraveling (PDU) method of error reduction was described by Werner et al. (ibidem). The purpose of this method was to take advantage, of stability of quantum error, while performing quantum sampling computations, with many iterations of the same quantum circuit (of course the circuit was initialized after every measurement).

The method was described and tested for circuits implementing trigonometric functions with one parameter ϕ , which was the sum of angles set on phase shift gates applied on computing qubit.

The PDU function was then described as an interpolated function for set of pairs (x_D, ε_D) , where D is the encoded input of the circuit in a binary form, x_D is the sum of angles set on phase shift gates, and ε_D is the measured error on output.

This method could be repurposed to reduce errors on other computations that make use of quantum sampling—for example for quantum image encoding and decoding.

For this specific purpose the PDU matrix is created, with the size of the encoded image. For each field in the matrix an empty PDU function is created, and then all of them are calibrated with predetermined number of data (corresponding to shades of gray). This matrix of functions interpolated between collected coefficients could be applied on specific image without the previous knowledge of what images will be used for encoding. The PDU method is in our opinion essential for widespread use of quantum image processing algorithms.

Figure 1. The same image before (left), and after (right) encoding and reconstruction on IBM Nairobi quantum computer, with the use of LPIQE algorithm

Current physical implementations of quantum computers produce results, that cannot be viably used on Figure .

In this paper we want to discover the possibility of using neural networks, to refine PDU factors applied on a resulting image, to further bring the possibility of using quantum computers for image processing.

In an original experiment for every method a PDU function was created and calibrated using 6 or 51 different shades of gray. Then, the set of 50 images of size 8x8 was encoded and restored into quantum circuit.

The resulting images were compared with originals, and statistic values of std dev, mean square error, variance and R^2 were recorded. After that the PDU function was applied, and resulting image was once again compared with the original. WE recorded the significant increase of correlation factors (Pearson's r , Spearman's ρ and Kendall's τ), which proves that the method reduce the error, indeed.

Deep Learning for error reduction

The main scheme of using deep learning (DL) for error reduction is defined by us in two variants as follows. The first variant is to compute the PDU parameters and the second one is to model the PDU function directly. In the first variant the input for DL network are reconstructed images and the output are the parameters designated using the procedure described above. Since these parameters are the differences between original (homogeneous gray) and reconstructed images, using the data augmentation techniques we expect that the network will be able to higher the number of gray-levels and bettering the interpolation.

In the second variant we model the PDU function itself. It means, that on the input we give the reconstructed images and on the output we obtain the image after error reduction. For training we use the image after the reconstruction process and the original images as the Ground Truth.

We use the DL methods from the area of image processing, like Convolutional Neural Network, CNN, Deep Boltzman Machine, Deep Belief Networks (DBN), Deep Stacking Networks (DSN); recurrence cells like: Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), Long-Short-Term memory (LSTM) – see Suganyadevi et al. [5]. We also use the Transformer, which becomes more and more useful in the area of reidentification e.g., Bian et al. [6]. The interesting for our purpose is GAN (Generative Adversarial Network) e.g. Wei et al. [7]. It is combination of two networks of similar architecture. One of them is trained to solve the given problem while the other one is trained to distinguish between the real object and those, generated by the first network.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge that this paper has been written based on the results achieved within the WrightBroS project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation pro-gramme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No 822483. Disclaimer: The paper reflects only the authors' view, and the Research Executive Agency (REA) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

References

- [1] K. Werner, K. Wereszczyński, i A. Michalczuk, „Experiment-Driven Quantum Error Reduction”, w *Computational Science – ICCS 2022*, D. Groen, C. de Mulatier, M. Paszynski, V. V. Krzhizhanovskaya, J. J. Dongarra, i P. M. A. Sloot, Red., w *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 13353. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, s. 195–201. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-08760-8_17.

- [2] P. Q. Le, F. Dong, i K. Hirota, „A flexible representation of quantum images for polynomial preparation, image compression, and processing operations”, *Quantum Inf. Process.*, t. 10, nr 1, s. 63–84, luty 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11128-010-0177-y.
- [3] Y. Zhang, K. Lu, Y. Gao, i M. Wang, „NEQR: a novel enhanced quantum representation of digital images”, *Quantum Inf. Process.*, t. 12, nr 8, s. 2833–2860, sie. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s11128-013-0567-z.
- [4] K. Wereszczyński, A. Michalczuk, D. Pęszor, M. Paszkuta, K. Cyran, i A. Polański, „Cosine series quantum sampling method with applications in signal and image processing”, *ArXiv201112738 Quant-Ph*, lis. 2020, Dostęp: 5 grudzień 2020. [Online]. Dostępne na: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2011.12738>
- [5] S. Suganyadevi, V. Seethalakshmi, i K. Balasamy, „A review on deep learning in medical image analysis”, *Int. J. Multimed. Inf. Retr.*, t. 11, nr 1, s. 19–38, mar. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s13735-021-00218-1.
- [6] S. Bian, M. Liu, B. Zhou, i P. Lukowicz, „The State-of-the-Art Sensing Techniques in Human Activity Recognition: A Survey”, *Sensors*, t. 22, nr 12, s. 4596, cze. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22124596.
- [7] L. Wei, S. Zhang, W. Gao, i Q. Tian, „Person Transfer GAN to Bridge Domain Gap for Person Re-identification”, w *2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Salt Lake City, UT, USA: IEEE, cze. 2018, s. 79–88. doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2018.00016.

* We would like to acknowledge that this paper has been written based on the results achieved within the WrightBroS project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No 822483. Supplementarily, this research work has been co-financed from Polish financial resources for science in 2019-2023 conferred for implementation of the co-financed international project. Disclaimer: The paper reflects only the authors' view and the Research Executive Agency (REA) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.